

Effects of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Powered Personalized Learning Platforms On Students' Academic Interest and Achievement.

JEMIRIGBE, Esther¹ & Prof. Ado, Isaac B.²

^{1&2} Department of Science Education

Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

jemiester222@gmail.com & adoib@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17237430>

Abstracts

This study investigated the effect of AI-powered personalized learning platform on students interest and achievement in physics(electromagnetism) among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa state. This goal compares students academic performance in AI-powered personalized learning platform to that of students in conventional learning platform. Three research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 1564 senior secondary school (II) physics students. A sample size of 87 students were used for the study. Sample was gotten from two schools selected using simple random sampling from the population. One school serves as the experimental group while the other as the control group. The instrument for data collection were Physics Achievement Test(PAT), Reasoning Ability Test (RAT) and Physics Interest Inventory(SII), which was developed by the researcher and validated by two experts in physics education and measurement and evaluation experts. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument and a reliability index of 0.74 and 0.73 were obtained for PAT and RAT. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test for the null hypotheses. The null hypothesis was rejected if probability value is less than the significant value of 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) and if otherwise ($P > 0.05$), it was not rejected. The findings of the study showed among others that physics student taught electromagnetism using AI-powered personalized learning platform had improved academic achievement more than those taught using conventional method. In line with the findings, the researcher recommended among others that schools should adopt the use of AI-powered personalized learning platform for teaching and learning physics (electromagnetism), to enhance students' academic achievement.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence in Education, Personalized Learning, Education Technology, Student Interest and Student Achievement

Introduction

Physics is one of the most fundamental sciences, and its importance reaches into nearly every aspect of modern life. It is the basis for many other sciences like chemistry, astronomy, and biology and most modern technology (smartphones, computers, GPS), medical devices relies on its principles. The design of bridges, buildings, and machines uses the principles of Physics. This results to the importance of this subject in the school sector. However, a lot have been spoken of the abstract and difficult nature of the subject. This has resulted to students lack of interest in the subject (Ankeli, Eriba & Achor, 2020; Bileya & Achor, 2021).

Interest involves personal curiosity, enthusiasm, or fascination that an individual has for that particular topic. It implies a desire to learn more, engage deeply, and explore various aspects of the

subject matter. Interest is defined by Igweh (2014), as an individual trait which determines a student vim and vigor in the pursuits of educational activities. Student interest is critical in the teaching and learning process, this is because interest derives curiosity, engagement, commitment and the determination to succeed. It fuels curiosity, encouraging students to seek out information independently and become lifelong learners. Students who are interested in a subject often use effective learning strategies such as elaboration, self-questioning, and making connections. This reduces distractions, allowing for deeper concentration and less cognitive fatigue. It makes students tend to pay more attention to materials when they find it interesting and this helps with information retention, comprehension and better academic achievement.

Academic achievement refers to the measurable outcomes of learning and educational progress attained by students within an academic setting. This achievement can include various aspects such as grades, standardized test scores, completion of assignments, projects, awards and other recognition related to academic pursuits. Academic achievement of student according to Chukkwu, Nwanne & Agommuoh (2017). It is the ability of the student to gain useful knowledge as well as communicate this gained knowledge orally or in written format. The achievement of students in Physics have not in recent years greatly improved (Akanbi et al, 2022). According to Akanbi et al (2022), the unstable physics learning achievement of students can be caused by several basic things such as lack of quantity and quality of physics teachers, inadequate equipment and laboratory facilities, lack of appropriate physics textbooks, and inappropriate teaching methods used in teaching, among others. Despite the importance of physics as an instrument for technological and scientific advancements of a country, the performance of learners in physics at the senior secondary school stage has not over the years been satisfactory. Unstable physics learning achievement of students can be caused by several basic things such as lack of quantity and quality of physics teachers, inadequate equipment and laboratory facilities, lack of appropriate physics textbooks, and inappropriate teaching methods used in teaching, among others. They further stated that the teaching method that a teacher embraces and the resources and materials available the teacher uses in teaching are issues that may affect the achievement of students.

The dynamic landscape of contemporary education is witnessing a transformative era driven by the convergence of advanced technologies and teaching methods. The rapid evolution of technology has led to the development of innovative tools that caters to diverse students' needs. The acceleration of technological progress has propelled artificial intelligence (AI) into various domains, and education stands as a prime factor for its transformative impact. AI plays a significant role in both general and higher education, influencing students' academic achievement and development by offering a mix of opportunities and challenges (Edtech, 2020). It is the area of teaching and learning that AI educational technologies are expected to have the most transformative impact (Rodway and Schepman, 2023). The influence of AI on education is transformative and multifaceted. From personalized learning experiences to intelligent tutoring systems that provide tailored guidance, support, and feedback based on individual learning patterns and knowledge levels (Hwang et al., 2020). One of AI's most revolutionary contribution is the ability to personalize learning experiences, which opens up new possibilities for adjusting instruction to meet the needs of specific students.

Personalized learning is an educational approach that tailor's instruction to meet the individual needs, skills and interest of each student (Shemshack & Spector, 2020). AI enables personalized learning by adapting educational content to meet the unique needs of individual students (Hennekeuser et al., 2024). This method emphasizes student-centric learning experiences, where

pace and instruction content are customized to suit each learner's abilities, needs and interest (Bernacki et al. 2021). The core idea is to move from the traditional one-size-fits-all instructional model and instead create a more engaging and effecting learning environment that acknowledge diverse backgrounds and abilities of students. Personalized learning has gained momentum with AI's incorporation. Through intelligent algorithms, data analysis and adaptive learning systems, AI can assess students' performance, academic achievement, predict learning outcomes and provide personalized feedback and resources, ensuring that learners can advance at their own speed (Meryem B., 2024).

The researched work "The Role of AI personalized learning" by Claned 2024 has shown that personalized learning can positively influence both student interest and academic performance by providing immediate feedback, AI-powered platforms help students identify areas for improvement, which can increase students' confidence and motivation. The interactive nature of AI personalized instructions platforms often involving simulations, virtual labs, and other multimedia resources that makes learning more engaging, potentially boosting students' interest in science subjects. Studies suggest that when students receive instruction tailored to their specific learning needs, they are more likely to remain engaged and persist in their learning (Pane et al., 2017; Means et al., 2010; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

AI- personalized instruction tools as intelligent tutoring systems, educational robots, learning analytics dashboards, adaptive learning platforms, and human-computer interactions have demonstrated significant potential for enhancing teaching and learning (Chen et al., 2020; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). For example, intelligent tutoring systems have been shown to provide personalized feedback and support, improving student engagement and learning outcomes (Luckin et al., 2016). Similarly, adaptive learning platforms leverage AI to tailor educational content to individual learners' needs, promoting more effective and efficient learning experiences (Holmes et al., 2019).

Moreover, personalized learning platforms are associated with improved achievement outcomes. In science, where students often face challenges in understanding abstract concepts such as chemical reactions or physics principles, these platforms offer the opportunity for learners to engage with content at their own pace, thus promoting mastery rather than superficial understanding. Research has consistently indicated that students who engage with adaptive learning technologies tend to show higher levels of achievement in both traditional assessments and problem-solving scenarios (Kulik & Fletcher, 2016). By leveraging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics, these platforms have the potential to significantly enhance students' reasoning abilities. Students' reasoning ability is a critical cognitive skill that enables students to analyse information, evaluate evidence and draw logical conclusion (Halpern, 2024). In the context of physics education in teaching Electromagnetism, reasoning ability plays a vital role in problem-solving, critical thinking and scientific inquiry (Reif & Larkin, 1991). AI powered personalized learning platforms can potentially enhance students' reasoning ability by providing tailored learning experiences, real-time feedback and adaptive assessments. Student have found that AI-powered platform can improve students critical thinking and problem solving skills (Griffin & Care, 2015). research has reveal that students cognitive abilities which include reasoning abilities can influence their engagement and motivation in learning (Pintrich 2003).

This research seeks to explore the effects of AI-powered personalized learning platforms on students' interest and achievement in science (physics) education.

Statement of the Problem

Despite numerous reforms and innovations in science education, students often struggle with low engagement and poor academic performance. Many learners perceive science as a difficult and uninteresting subject due to rigid curricula and one-size-fits-all instructional approaches. These issues contribute to declining interest in science career and poor achievement outcomes national and international assessments like West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO).

Artificial intelligence offers the potential to revolutionize learning by providing personalized experiences that cater to individual student needs. However, there is a limited body of empirical evidence assessing the impact of AI-powered personalized learning on student interest and achievement in science education particularly at the secondary school level. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by examining how the use of AI-powered personalized learning platform affects students' interest and their academic achievement in Physics.

Aim and objectives of the Study

The study aim to examine the effects of AI-powered personalized learning platform on students' interest and academic achievement in science among secondary schools in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state. Specifically, the study examined:

- i. the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.
- ii. the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.
- iii. the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What are the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method?
- ii. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method?
- iii. What are the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.
- iii. There is no significant difference among the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms.

Research Methodology

The study adopted the Quasi-experimental research design using the pre-test and post-test control group approach. The experimental group was taught using AI-powered personalized learning platform, while the control group was taught using conventional teacher-led instruction. The population consisted of all 1564 senior secondary school two Physics students in Ogbia local government area. A sample of 87 students were used for the study. The sample was gotten from two

schools selected using simple random sampling from the population. One school served as the experimental group while the other served as the control group.

The instrument for data collection were Physics achievement test (PAT), Reasoning Ability Test (RAT) and Physics Interest Inventory (SII). PAT consisted of two sections, section A and B. Section A consist of demographic information of the subjects and section B consisted of 30 multiple-choice items designed to assess students' knowledge in Electricity (electromagnetism) in Physics. RAT consisted of two sections, sections A and B. Section A consisted of demographic information and section B consisted of 25 items on quantitative reasoning ability. The quartile was used to classed the students into high, average and low reason ability. SII was an inventory of students' interest in Physics; SII consisted of two sections, sections A and B. Section A consisted of demographic information and section B consisted of 10 items on Physics interest.

The instruments were subjected to both content and face validation by two experts in Physics education and Measurement and Evaluation experts, they reviewed the questions and made necessary contributions which were reflected in the final draft of the instrument to be used. The reliability of PAT and RAT were determined using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), and reliabilities coefficient of 0.74 and 0.73 were obtained for PAT and RAT respectively. A reliability of 0.81 was obtained for SII using Cronbach Alpha coefficient formula.

The two groups were taught the same concepts and topics for the period of six weeks after which the items in the instrument used for pre-test was rearranged and used for post-test. The mode of test administration for this study involved a pre-test and post-test approach to assess students' achievement in physics (Electromagnetism). The pre-test was administered at the beginning of the course or unit on electromagnetism to establish baseline understanding. It was conducted in the classroom setting, with student completing the test individually, without access to notes, to ensure an accurate measure of their current knowledge. The post test was administered after the AI-Powered personalized learning platform was implemented. Both test were standardized covering key concepts on electromagnetism and were supervised by trained research assistants to ensure consistency and reliability of the data collected. Concurrently conventional physics teachers were trained on implementing the AI-Powered personalized learning platform to teach students in the experimental group. A lesson plan centered around electromagnetism was devised. Student interest were assessed using a structured questionnaires to gather data on student preferences and engagement. The teacher also observes the students' engagement during electromagnetism lessons and discussions to gauge interest.

Results

The results are presented in tables based on the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What are the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method?

Table 1: Adjusted Mean Interest and Standard Deviation Scores of Students Taught with AI-powered personalized learning platforms and Conventional Method in Physics Using Pretest as Covariate.

Method	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
AI-powered personalized learning platforms	41	2.86	0.40
Conventional	46	2.30	0.48

Results in Table 1 shows that the mean interest scores of students taught Electromagnetism using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and conventional methods are 2.48 and 2.12 respectively. From the result, it could be inferred that those taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms had a higher mean interest score than those taught using convectional.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method?**Table 2: Adjusted Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students Taught Using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and Conventional Method in Physics with Pretest as Covariate.**

Method	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
AI-powered personalized learning platforms	41	24.80	2.04
Conventional	46	21.20	2.62

Results in Table 2 shows that the mean achievement scores of students taught Electromagnetism using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and conventional methods are 24.80 and 21.20 respectively. From the result, it could be inferred that those taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms had a higher mean achievement score than those taught using convectional.

Research Question 3

What are the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms?

Table 3: Adjusted Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Students with Different Ability Level Taught Using AI-Powered Personalized Learning Platforms with Pretest as Covariate

Gender	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
High	8	24.91	1.13
Average	23	24.71	2.12
Low	10	24.84	2.57

Results in Table 3 shows that the mean achievement score of students having high, average and low ability taught electromagnetism using using AI-powered personalized learning platforms are 24.91, 24.71 and 24.84 respectively. The result indicates that students having high ability had the highest mean score, followed by average ability and low ability had the least.

Hypotheses

Hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance

Hypotheses One

There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Interest Scores of Students Taught Using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and Conventional Method in Physics with Pretest as Covariate.

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	11.83	1	11.83	78.45	.00
Main Effects	Methods	5.51	1	5.51	36.52	.00
Residual		12.67	84	.15		
Total		30.01	86	.35		

In Table 4, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .00 of Methods is less than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P < .05$, there significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Achievement Scores of Students Taught Using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and Conventional Method in Physics with Pretest as Covariate.

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	7.05	1	7.05	1.28	.26
Main Effects	Method	279.94	1	279.94	50.78	.00
Residual		463.07	84	5.51		
Total		750.07	86	8.72		

In Table 5, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .00 of method is less than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P < .05$, there exist significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference among the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Scores of Students with Different Ability Taught Using AI-integrated Flipped Classroom Models with Pretest as Covariate

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	1.06	1	1.06	0.24	.63
Main Effects	Ability	0.25	2	0.13	0.03	.97
Residual		165.71	37	4.48		
Total		167.02	40	4.18		

In Table 6, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .97 of Ability of is greater than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that at $P < .05$, there exist no significant difference among the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms.

Discussion

The findings from the results on the difference between the mean interest scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method indicated a significant difference. Students taught the concept of electricity (electromagnetism) using AI-powered personalized learning platforms performed significantly better than those taught using conventional method. The findings could be attributed to AI-powered personalized learning platforms fueling the curiosity of students and encouraging them to seek out information independently and become lifelong learners. This may have resulted to elaboration, self-questioning, and making connections thereby reducing distractions, allowing for deeper concentration and less cognitive fatigue. This affirms Shemshack and Spector (2020), who stated that Personalized learning is an educational approach that tailor's instruction to meet the individual needs, skills and interest of each student. The findings are in line with that of Shemshack and Spector (2020), who reported that AI-powered personalized learning platform result in higher academic performance compared to traditional method.

The findings from the results on the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms and those taught using conventional method indicated a significant difference. The findings could be attributed to AI-powered personalized learning platforms emphasizing student-centric learning experiences, where pace and instruction content are customized to suit each learner's abilities, needs and interest (Bernacki et al. 2021). It may have been from AI-powered personalized learning platforms creating a more engaging and effecting learning environment that acknowledge diverse backgrounds and abilities of students. Personalized learning has gained momentum with AI's incorporation. Through intelligent algorithms, data analysis and adaptive learning systems, AI can assess students' performance, academic achievement, predict learning outcomes and provide personalized feedback and resources, ensuring that learners can advance at their own speed (Meryem B., 2024). The findings are in line with that of Meryem B., 2024.

The findings from the results on the difference among the mean achievement scores of students with different reasoning ability level taught using AI-powered personalized learning platforms indicated a non-significant difference. The findings could be attributed to AI-powered personalized learning platforms predicting students' learning outcomes and provide personalized feedback and resources, ensuring that learners can advance at their own speed. The findings are in line with that of Pintrich 2003.

Conclusion

Integrating AI-Powered personalized learning platforms can lead to substantial improvements in both academic performance and student motivation. This can be particularly beneficial in under-resourced educational settings where personalized instruction is difficult to achieve through traditional methods. In education AI enables personalized learning experiences by tailoring instruction to meet individual student needs, fostering engagement and providing immediate feedback to help student track their progress and areas needing improvement. The study concludes that AI-Powered personalized learning platforms have a positive effect on students' interest and achievement in electromagnetism among secondary school in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendation were proffered:

1. Schools should adopt the use of AI-powered personalized learning platforms for teaching and learning.
2. Future research should explore the long-term effect off AI-based educational tools on student outcomes and investigate how these tools can be integrated with traditional teaching methods to maximize benefits.
3. Teachers should be trained on how to effectively use AI-powered personalized learning platform to support student learning
4. Schools should invest in developing the necessary infrastructure to support the use of AI-powered personalized learning platforms

References

- Akanbi, A. O., Mohammed, R. E., Yusuf, A. A. & Olayinka, Y. W. (2022). Effects of hands-on instructional strategy on senior school students' performance in waves. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)* 16(3), 366~374. DOI: 10.11591/edulearn.v16i3.20320
- Ankeli, G. O., Eriba, J. O. & Achor, E. E.(2020). Increasing self-efficacy of secondary school students in physics using mentoring enhanced strategy. *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer Science*, 1(2), 27-36. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367568921_
- Bernacki, M. L., Greene, M. J., & Lobezowski, N. G. (2021). A systematic review of research on personalized learning: Personalized by whom, to what, how, and for what purpose (s)? *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(4), 1675-1715
- Bileya, S. G. & Achor, E. E. (2021). Relative effectiveness of concept mapping strategy and guided discovery meth- od in enhancing students' interest in Physics. *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer Science*,2(2), 1-11. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367568921_

- Chen, Zhonghan, Juxiao Zhang, Xiaoyan Jiang, Zuojin HU, Xue Han, Menyyang Xu, V. Savitha, and G.N. Vivekananda. "Education 4.0 using artificial intelligence for student performance analysis." *Intelligence Artificial* , Vol.23, Issue. 66, pp.124-137, 2020.
- Griffin, P., 7 Care, E. (Eds). (2015). *Assessment and Teaching of 21st Century Skills: Methods and approach*. Springer.
- Hennekeuser, D., Vaziri, D., Golchinfar, D., Schreiber, D., & Stevens, G. (2024). Enlarge Education-Exploring the Use of Generative AI to Support Lecturing in Higher Education. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* , 1-33
- Holmes, W., Chakroun, B., Miao, F. Mendes, V. Domiter, A., Fan, H., ... & Assouline, N. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Development Synthesis Report*. Mobile Learning Week 2019.
- Hwang, Gwo-Jen, Haoran Xie, Benjamin W. Wah, & Dragan Gasevic. "Vision, challenges, roles and research issues on Artificial Intelligence in Education." *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence* 1, 100001, 2020.
- Kulik, J.A., & Fletcher, J. D. (2016). Effectiveness of intelligence tutoring systems: a meta-analytic review. *Review of educational research*, 86(1), 42-78 doi: <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315581420>
- Meryem, B., (2024). The role of artificial intelligence in personalized learning: Shaping the future of education. <https://www.visionfactory.org/post/the-role-of-artificial-intelligence-in-personalized-learning-shaping-future-of-education>
- Pane, J. F., Steiner E. D., Baird M. D., Hamilton, L. S., & Pane, J. D. (2017). *how does personalized learning affect student achievement?* RAND Corporation. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_briefs/RB9994.html
- Pintrich, P. R. (2003). A Motivational Science Perspective on the Role of Student Motivation in Learning and Teaching Contexts. *Journal of Educational Psychology* 95 (4), 667-686
- Rodway, P., & Schepman, A. (2023). The Impact of Adopting Educational Technologies on Projected Course Satisfaction in University Students. *Computers and education: Artificial intelligence*, 5, 100150. Doi:10.1016/j.caea i.2023.100150
- Shemshack, Atikah & Jonathan Michael Sector. "A systematic literature review of personalized learning terms." *Smart Learning Environment*, Vol.7, Issue.1,pp.1-20,2020
- Zawacki Richter, V.I. Marin, M. Bond, F. Gouverneur (2019). Systematic Review of Research on Artificial Intelligence Application in Higher Education-where are the educators? *International journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16 (1) (2019), pp. 1-27, 10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0